

Detailed workflow: a step-by-step guide to ground-based photogrammetry of forested streams (Agisoft Metashape)

A Metashape Processing Report (PDF) is provided to document all reconstruction settings, software version, and computing environment used to generate the example outputs (see outputs files).

1 - Data Processing with Metashape

Step 1: Setting Up the Project (~10min)

1. Open Agisoft Metashape :

- Launch the software on your computer.

2. Add Photos:

- Go to **Workflow > Add Photos**.
- Select all the images captured with the action camera.
- Click **Open** to import the images into the project.

3. Set the Coordinate System:

- If your images include georeferencing information or you are working in a known coordinate system, select it under **Reference Settings**.
- For data from Quebec, consider using an appropriate projected coordinate system such as **NAD83 / Quebec Lambert (EPSG:32198)** if it suits your study area.

Step 2: Aligning the Photos (~15 min)

1. Photo Alignment Settings:

- Go to **Workflow > Align Photos**.
- Under **Accuracy**, select **High** (a good balance between processing time and accuracy; choose **Highest** if you have a powerful machine and want the best possible alignment).
- **Key point limit**: Set this to around **80,000** to ensure sufficient feature detection.
- **Tie point limit**: Set this to about **4,000** to maintain a manageable number of tie points without overwhelming the project.

These settings typically provide a good balance: the key point limit is high enough to capture fine details of the stream bed and banks, while the tie point limit helps control for noise and reduce processing overhead.

2. **Start the Alignment:**

- Click **OK** to begin photo alignment.
- Wait for the alignment process to complete. Depending on the number of photos and system performance, this step may take approximately 10–20 minutes.

Step 3: Building the Point Cloud (~30 min)

1. **Build Point Cloud:**

- Go to **Workflow > Build Point Cloud**.
- Choose a **Quality** setting. We recommend **Medium** quality for a reasonable trade-off between processing speed and detail. Higher settings (e.g., High) offer more detail but significantly increase computation time.

- **Depth Filtering:** Select **Mild** depth filtering. This setting usually strikes a good balance between smoothing out noise and retaining important details in complex stream environments.

2. Run the Process:

- Click **OK** to start building the Point cloud.
- Allow the process to complete. Processing times vary based on image count and computer performance.

3. Save the Project:

- Go to **File > Save As**.
- Name your project (e.g., “DSM_Model”) and click **Save**.

Step 4: Building the Textured Model (~15 min)

1. Build Mesh (if desired):

- **Workflow > Build Mesh**
- Use the Point Cloud as the source.
- Select a **Face Count** (e.g., Medium) to produce a detailed yet manageable mesh.

2. Build Texture:

- **Workflow > Build Texture**
- Use default settings or adjust as necessary for better texture quality.
- Click **OK** to generate the textured model.

Step 5: Creating the Orthomosaic (~10 min)

1. Build Orthomosaic:

- Go to **Workflow > Build Orthomosaic**.
- If you have georeferenced images or GCPs, choose the appropriate **Projection** (e.g., NAD83 / Quebec Lambert).
- If no georeferencing is available, select a **Planar** projection (Top XY) to generate a relative (non-georeferenced) orthomosaic.

2. Start the Process:

- Click **OK** to begin.
- Wait for the orthomosaic generation to complete.

3. Complete and Save:

- Once finished, **File > Export Orthomosaic** to your preferred format and location.

Always use a coordinate system appropriate for your region and data sources to ensure better accuracy in analyses. Higher-quality settings (Highest accuracy, High dense cloud) demand more processing power and time. If your hardware is limited, opt for lower-quality settings. If initial results are unsatisfactory, consider adding artificial targets, adjusting camera angles, or using different key/tie point limits to improve alignment and reconstruction quality.